

PSYCHOSOMATIC DISEASES AND THEIR STUDY

D.Q.Matkarimova

Urganch State University

2nd year master's student in psychology (by types of activity).

G.Sh.Nurjonova

Urganch State University

2nd year master's student in psychology (by types of activity).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7572080>

Annotation: this article provides information about psychosomatic diseases and the factors that cause them and the history of their study.

Key words: Psychosomatics, psyche, emotions, emotions, medical history.

Today, our country is implementing reforms to improve human health. In particular, PQ-4063, adopted on December 18, 2018, "On measures to prevent non-communicable diseases, support a healthy lifestyle and increase the level of physical activity of the population, and 2019 Our decision No. PQ-4190 dated December 13 "On approval of the concept of development of the mental health care service of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025" is a clear proof of our opinion[1].

Today, especially psychosomatic diseases belong to the group of diseases that pose a great threat to human health.

Psychosomatic diseases are a group of diseases caused by mental changes in the patient's nervous system with symptoms similar to diseases of internal organs [2].

Diseases belonging to the psychosomatic group are determined by the influence of a number of factors.

The social environment, stressors, social crises, information flow, negative family and interpersonal relationships affect the human psyche and cause psychological disorders. In each period, specific psychological diseases appear and develop. For this reason, the study of psychosomatic diseases, duodenum and gastric ulcer is a relevant topic. Our relationship to the external environment, that is, our reactions and emotions, affects our health. Mental states of panic, anger, guilt, fear, suppressed anger, grief, sadness, anxiety, all of these activate the mechanism of "squeezing" in the body, as a result of which diseases belonging to the group of various psychosomatic diseases arise and develop.

Humans have negative emotions as well as positive emotions, and these emotions cannot be avoided. Negative emotions are dangerous because they cause diseases. For example, suppressed anger turns into pain, and then makes the body sick. Often the liver, if anger is directed at oneself or at others, problems with the heart and blood system appear. Hidden pain and unspoken complaints can lead to persistent cough and even chronic bronchitis. If aggressive anger is suppressed for a long time, then there is a sudden fear, attacks of shortness of breath, these are symptoms of bronchial asthma. If fear, pain, anger and other negative emotions are constantly present, diseases of the stomach, intestines, kidneys, heart, thyroid gland and other organs appear[3].

Psychologists Cheek and Lecorn in 1968 described the causes of psychosomatic diseases as follows.

1. Conflict - the internal conflict between different psychological situations of a person can lead to the formation of a psychosomatic symptom.

2. A body language message is a metaphorical message about an unresolved psychological problem (for example: "I can't handle it").

3. Benefit from illness - this category includes health problems that bring some kind of conditional benefit to their owner or someone close to him.

4. Wound - the cause of the disease can be a past traumatic experience (betrayal, rejection, abandonment, humiliation, injustice).

5. Identification - can be formed as a result of identification with a person (hero, parent, mentor) who wants to be like a physical person (but sometimes, on the contrary, there is a strong unwillingness to be similar). Often this person is already dead, and then identifying with him allows you to maintain a relationship with him.

6. Self-punishment - in some cases, a psychosomatic symptom plays the role of unconscious self-punishment for real or imaginary guilt. In addition, unconsciously trying to punish another person with their suffering can make them feel guilty.

7. Suggestion - Symptoms are presented by an authority figure (for example, a parent, doctor, professor) can be triggered by a suggestion of negative belief [4].

Analyzing the above reasons, any types of psychosomatic diseases can be caused by the inability to express the arising nervous tension, which, as a result, manifests itself at the level of the body.

If we look at the history of the study of psychosomatic diseases, many thinking scientists have mentioned it in their works.

The concept of psychosomatics began to be used scientifically almost 200 years ago, although it is not possible to interpret it in a clear way. In Greek philosophy, there was a very common idea about the soul and the influence of the soul on the body. , it will also be good, if it is good with the head, it will be good for the whole body, and the body cannot be healed without the soul. Because everything comes from the heart, both good and bad, both in the body and in the whole person... And the soul should be treated with special healing conversations...». However, these healing conversations must be beautiful speeches (logoi kaloi). Due to this type of speech, prudence prevails in the heart. What Plato is talking about in this dialogue, modern ideas define the possibilities of psychosomatic thinking and response: "we can say to a young man that he is lucky with his headache, because by treating his head he can improve his whole mental life!".

Ibn Sina said that the origin of diseases depends on the nervous system, that anger, fear, and strong stress weaken the body and cause this. Ibn Sina's theory about the importance of the nervous system in controlling the body's activity is very similar to the theory of nervousness created by European scientists at the beginning of the 20th century. Ibn Sina proved in many experiments that the pulse depends on the activity of the nervous system. He diagnosed many diseases based on pulse. Ibn Sina not only studied the specific characteristics of pulse in various diseases, but also described changes in pulse in various emotional stress and nervous diseases. In the treatises of Ibn Sina, one can find information about how nerve centers receive information from internal organs through special nerve fibers and control their activity. Ibn Sina's views on the unity of the body and the soul are now fully confirmed due to the achievements of modern medicine, and the science called psychosomatic medicine was founded [5].

The establishment of psychological support in somatic clinics at the beginning of the 20th century gave a great impetus to the development of psychosomatic medicine in Europe and the USA.

The term "psychosomatics" was first introduced in 1818 by the German doctor Logan Christian Heinroth.

Z. Freud wrote: "If we kick a problem out the door, it climbs in through the window as a sign." Psychosomatics is based on a psychological defense mechanism called regression, that is, we try not to think about problems, to put them aside, not to analyze them and not to meet them face to face. The problems transferred in this way rise from the level of emergence, that is, from the social (interpersonal relations) or psychological (unfulfilled desires and aspirations, suppressed emotions, internal contradictions) to the level of the physical body [6].

The following scientific schools made a great contribution to the development of psychosomatic medical problems:

1. In America, the theoretical foundations of psychosomatics were developed based on psychoanalytic concepts (F. Alexander, H.F. Dunbar, I. Weiss and G. Engel);
2. Researched the philosophical foundations of psychosomatics in Germany (W. Von Krehl, von Weissacher, von Bergman);
3. The study of psychosomatic diseases in Russia is based on the teachings of I.P. Pavlov (Pavlov on higher nervous activity).

Since the beginning of the 20th century, I.P. Pavlov has shown the importance of the central nervous system in controlling somatic functions in a number of his works. K. Anokhin, a follower of I. Pavlov, who contributed to the further development of this problem, created the theory of functional systems of the organism. This made it possible to assess the role of emotions and motives in the development of somatic diseases from a new point of view [7].

So, based on the above ideas, psychosomatic diseases are a separate group, their origin and progression depend on psychological factors. Psychosomatic disease has been studied both in ancient times and in modern medical psychology. Due to the fact that mental states depend on the social environment, the study of psychosomatic diseases is an important task even today.

References:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 1992.
2. Psychosomatic Medicine - Wikipedia (wikipedia.org);
3. Psychosomatic diseases (everaoh.com);
4. Psychosomatic medicine - Wikipedia (wikipedia.org);
5. Ibodullayev.Z "Medical psychology" Tashkent "New century generation" 2009;
6. Main psychosomatic diseases. Article. Anti-stress program. Self-knowledge.ru * Family and children (perestanolki.org);
7. Main psychosomatic diseases. Article. Anti-stress program. Self-knowledge.ru * Family and children (perestanolki.org);

